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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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ISSUES OF DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF AN ANDRAGOGICAL APPROACH

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Abstract: The significance of the andragogical approach in the modern system of pedagogical education is highlighted, particularly its role in developing communicative competence among future teachers. The impact of andragogical methods on fostering stable communication skills and personal development is analyzed. Based on theoretical perspectives and both national and international experience, scientific conclusions and practical recommendations are presented.

Key words: andragogy, communicative competence, future teacher, interactive methods, pedagogical communication.

Annotatsiya: Andragogik yondashuvning zamonaviy pedagogika tizimidagi o'rni, ayniqsa, bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda kommunikativ kompetentlikni shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati yoritiladi. Talabalarni yetuk shaxs sifatida tarbiyalash hamda ularda barqaror muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda andragogik metodlarning ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, nazariy qarashlar, xorijiy va milliy tajribalar asosida ilmiy xulosalar va amaliy takliflar bayon etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: andragogika, kommunikativ kompetentlik, bo'lajak o'qituvchi, interaktiv metodlar, pedagogik muloqot.

Аннотация: Раскрывается значение андрагогического подхода в современной системе педагогического образования, в частности, его роль в формировании коммуникативной компетентности будущих учителей. Проанализировано влияние андрагогических методов на развитие устойчивых коммуникативных навыков и воспитание личности студента. На основе теоретических положений, а также отечественного и зарубежного опыта представлены научные выводы и практические рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: андрагогика, коммуникативная компетентность, будущий учитель, интерактивные методы, педагогическое общение.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the modernization of the education system requires the formation of a teacher not only as a provider of knowledge, but also as an active communicator in the socio-cultural environment. In this regard, the formation of communicative competence of a teacher in the pedagogical education system is one of the most urgent problems. Such competences include not only the ability to provide knowledge to students, but also the skills of directing them correctly, motivating them, and creating a positive emotional climate.

The andragogical approach is considered an effective methodology for working with adult learners. This approach involves drawing on the student's previous experience and engaging them as active participants in the learning process. Therefore, the development of communicative competence through the andragogical approach is regarded as an important strategic direction in the training of pedagogical personnel.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Andragogy is a person-centered, experience- and needs-based model of education that considers adult learners as independent, responsible, and conscious individuals. By applying this approach in higher education institutions, future teachers develop the following skills:

- expressing ideas clearly,
- active listening and emotional empathy,

- confidence in social interactions,
- critical thinking and a diplomatic approach.

Within the andragogical approach, teachers develop a culture of communication through students' independent decision-making, problem-based learning, role-playing, training, and reflective exercises.

According to international experience, in developed countries such as the USA, Germany, and Finland, courses such as communication psychology, conflict-free communication, and effective speech techniques are included in teacher training based on andragogy. In the context of Uzbekistan, methodological foundations for the development of this approach are currently being formed.

In modern pedagogy, the development of a teacher's communicative competence is one of the most pressing issues, especially in the context of digital transformation, the influence of social networks, and interactive learning environments. In addition to acquiring knowledge and skills, a future teacher should be a mature individual who can express ideas fluently, clearly, and confidently, and select appropriate communication strategies in various situations.

The andragogical approach provides a strong scientific and practical basis for fulfilling these requirements. This approach values the learner's experience, recognizes them as independent thinking subjects, and promotes the "companion-teacher" model. As Knowles^[2] noted, the primary focus in working with adults should be on their intrinsic motivation and individual learning styles.

Furthermore, according to the theory of "transformative learning" developed by Mezirow^[5], an individual's worldview, values, and communicative approaches undergo fundamental changes during the educational process. For future teachers, this implies not only acquiring knowledge, but also developing self-understanding, respect for others' opinions, and a sense of social responsibility.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

An analysis of the experience of Uzbekistan shows that practical training aimed at developing communicative competence in pedagogical universities remains insufficient. Students demonstrate a low level of practical competence in public speaking, working with the public, and communicating with parents and colleagues. This situation hinders the preparation of teachers who are competitive in the labor market and capable of meeting modern demands.

In contrast, international practice allocates separate disciplines and experimental programs to the development of teachers' communication skills based on the andragogical approach. For example:

1. In Finland, each future teacher studies the course "Professional Communication and Reflection" and participates in socio-psychological training.
2. In German pedagogical faculties, "interactive seminars" are conducted every semester based on practical communication situations.
3. In South Korea, andragogy and media literacy are integrated into the teacher training system in a balanced and systematic manner.

Therefore, it is becoming an urgent task to introduce the following measures:

1. The development of integrated disciplines (speech culture + psychology + communication technologies) focused on communicative competence.
2. The implementation of informal education formats, such as training sessions and master classes, which are more effective than traditional lectures.
3. The use of practical simulations, including role-playing games and case studies that reflect student–parent, teacher–colleague, and teacher–administrator relationships.

In addition, digital communication and educational activities on social networks (edublogs, pedagogical content) are becoming key competencies for the new generation of teachers. Consequently, the andragogical approach is evolving into a comprehensive framework that addresses these emerging needs.

Andragogy is not merely a didactic model, but a system of principles aimed at personal, social, and communicative development. The formation of communicative competence in future teachers requires the systematic and strategic implementation of this approach. Practice-oriented integrated programs that teach communication in psychological, linguistic, and cultural contexts contribute to improving the overall quality of education.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Communicative competence is not limited to language knowledge; it also includes the correct organization of speech acts, understanding of context, and the appropriate use of facial expressions, intonation, and emotional background. In this regard, psycholinguistic knowledge serves to further improve the communicative approach of the teacher. The teacher must understand the social, cultural, and psychological subtext in each speech and be able to address the audience in an appropriate tone.

According to UNESCO [6], 42% of secondary school teachers are inactive in extracurricular communication due to uncertainty, communicative barriers, or psychological fatigue. Therefore, in global practice, improving the communicative competence of teachers is identified as a priority. In Uzbekistan, this indicator is not fully reflected in official statistics; however, the level of classroom activity and the student's subjective confidence directly depend on the communicative potential of the teacher.

Today, digital technologies are changing the way teachers communicate. For example, in online classes conducted on platforms such as Zoom or Google Meet, written communication is increasing through forums and electronic journals. Therefore, future teachers need to acquire skills such as online communication etiquette, the use of visual communication tools, and the creation of effective digital presentations.

The number of future teachers is predominantly female, which requires specific approaches to communication, including gentleness, empathy, and social sensitivity. Therefore, it is recommended to include separate training in gender differences, emotional intelligence, and empathetic listening within the andragogical approach.

Uzbek society has its own mentality, values, and forms of social communication. A future teacher should develop communicative competence not only on the basis of general theories, but also through practical exercises adapted to the local context. For example, participation in conversations with parents or involvement in public events serves as a real school of communication for students.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The development of communicative competence of future teachers is one of the most important strategic directions in modern education. In particular, the formation of this competence based on the andragogical approach is carried out by taking into account the age, life experience, social role, and independent thinking ability of students. The theoretical views and practical observations analyzed in this article demonstrate that effective communication is manifested not only as an exchange of knowledge between teacher and student, but also as a guarantee of trust, social cooperation, and the overall quality of education.

The following principles should be followed in developing communicative competence in students:

- communicating on the basis of mutual respect and empathy,
- combining digital and traditional means of communication,
- teaching effective communication with different social groups,
- encouraging reflection and critical thinking,
- harmonizing communication culture with national and global values.

Furthermore, the development of communicative competence not only increases the student's level of self-awareness, but also enhances the social significance of the education system. Therefore, the introduction of integrated curricula based on an andragogical approach and enriched with communicative training in pedagogical higher education institutions should be considered an urgent issue.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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